

Estimation of the actual evapotranspiration in olive orchard using a two-layer model integrating climate and satellite data

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Abstract

Traditionally, irrigation labor considers the value of reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) and crop coefficient to estimate actual evapotranspiration (ET_a). This methodology presents significant errors in the obtention of K_c . To avoid using empirical values of K_c , some authors suggest using two layer models to estimate ET_a over sparse canopies such as olive orchards. However, the model does not consider the effect of spatial variability corresponding to the size of the canopy, leaf area index (LAI) and fractional coverage (f_c) on the quantification of ET_a . For this reason, a study was carried out to estimate ET_a using the Shuttleworth-Wallace (SW) model over a drip irrigated olive orchard using as inputs climatic and satellite data. The experiment was performed over a 6.45 ha, processing 7 Landsat images acquired from 2009 to 2010. The information was used to calculate instantaneous net radiation (R_{n_i}) and instantaneous soil heat flux (G_i), which estimated the instantaneous available energy (A_i). The SW model performance was compared with the eddy-covariance (EC) method. Results indicate that ET_a estimated through climatic and remote sensing information (ET_{sw1}) shows an error of 10% with a RMSE and MAE values of 0.31 and 0.28 mm day⁻¹ respectively. For ET_a estimated through climatic information (ET_{sw2}) an error of 10% and a RMSE 24% higher than ET_{sw1} was observed, showing that the use of spatially distributed variables such as R_{n_i} and G_i could improve the performance of the proposed model.

Introduction

Several studies have indicated that water availability will be reduced significantly in the next decades due to a strong competition among agriculture, industry and urban areas (Molden, 2007; Bates, 2009). In central Chile, a reduction in the precipitation levels has been projected, with an expected reduction between 20-40%. Therefore, the stability and growth of agriculture, including the olive oil industry, will be significantly limited by water scarcity. Under this scenario, sophisticated irrigation management will be required to optimize water use efficiency and maintain sufficient levels of productivity and quality (Ortega-Farías et al., 2009). Also, it is important to consider both the total available water in a region seasonally, and the timing when water deficits are likely to occur, as a way to adjust water needs to the available resources (Passioura, 2006). For this, it is necessary to accurately estimate actual evapotranspiration (ET_a) which is generally computed as a function of a reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) and crop coefficient (K_c). (Allen et al., 1998, Ortega-Farías et al., 1995). This method provides a simple approach for the estimation of olive water requirements, but K_c values reported on literature are empirical and are not adapted to the orchard conditions of soil, climate, cultivar and training system (Ortega-Farías et al., 2009).

It is widely accepted that the use of Shuttleworth and Wallace model (SW) could be used to directly estimate ET_a (Anadranistakis et al., 2000; Ortega-Farías et al., 2010; Testi et al., 2004; Were et al., 2008; Zhou et al., 2006) as a way to avoid using empirical values of K_c . The SW model can estimate soil evaporation and transpiration separately and has been widely used on continuous and discontinuous crops such as sorghum (Kato and Kamichika 2006), corn (Anadranistakis et al. 2000; Gardiol et al. 2003), wheat (Anadranistakis et al. 2000), vineyards and olive orchards (Zhang et al., 2008; Ortega-Farías et al., 2006; Ortega-Farías et al. 2010). The SW model estimates ET_a as the sum of the Penman-Monteith equation for evaporation and transpiration, weighted by a set of

coefficients that account for the combination of soil and canopy resistances (Shuttleworth and Wallace 1985). For heterogeneous canopies such as vineyards and orchard, the SW model estimates ET_a with errors ranging from 6 to 25 percent (Zhang et al. 2008; Zhang, et al., 2009; Ortega-Farías et al. 2010; Ortega-Farías and Lopez-Olivari, 2012; Zhao et al., 2015). However, for irrigation management, the SW model does not consider the effect of spatial variability of soil and olive vigor on the estimation of ET_a . To include this effect on ET_a , ground-based weather measurements and remote sensing images could be used in the SW model as input data. Based on our knowledge, there is no available information regarding the estimation of ET_a using ground-based weather measurements in combination with remote sensing images. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to evaluate the two-layer model of SW to estimate actual evapotranspiration of a drip-irrigated olive orchard using ground-based weather measurements and remote sensing information obtained from a satellite platform.

Methods

Study site description

Measurements were done on a commercial olive orchard with drip irrigation (*Olea europaea* L. cv Arbequina) located in Pencoche, Maule Region, Chile (35° 23' S, 71° 44' W, WGS84, 96 m.a.s.l.) during 2009-2010 growing season. The study area has a Mediterranean climate, with a mean temperature of 14.8 °C and an accumulated ET_o of 1013 mm from September to May. The average annual rainfall is approximately 602 mm, falling principally during winter (May to September). The orchard was established in 2005, with a high density of 1,333 trees ha⁻¹ (5.0 m x 1.5 m of spacing). The trees are conducted on a monocone system with a height of 3.2 m and a canopy width of 1.55 m. The crop was irrigated by two drippers per tree (2.0 L h⁻¹) spaced at intervals of 0.75 m along the rows.

Two towers (4.8 m height) were installed on a homogeneous plot (6.4 ha) to measure surface energy balance components and micrometeorological variables at 30 minutes intervals. Latent (LE) and sensitive (H) heat fluxes were measured with an Eddy Covariance (EC) system, which is composed by a three-dimensional sonic anemometer (CSAT3, Campbell Scientific Inc., Logan, UT, USA) and an infrared gas analyzer (LI-7500, LI-COR Inc., Lincoln, Nebraska, USA). To correct the sonic temperature due to crosswind influences (Schotanus et al., 1983) and water vapor density due to influences of fluctuations in temperature and humidity (Webb et al., 1980), a post-process step was carried out.

Finally, remote sensing information (R_{n_i} and G_i) was obtained through the use of satellite images from Landsat 7. Values of R_{n_i} for each pixel at the time of the satellite overpass were estimated according to Allen et al., (1998) and instantaneous values of soil heat flux (G_i) were calculated using an empirical relation developed by Ortega-Farías et al., (2016).

Statistical analysis

The ratio of estimated to observed values (b), mean absolute error (MAE) and root-mean-square error (RMSE) (Mayer and Butler, 1993; Willmott et al., 1985) were used to perform the validation of the SW model to compute daily actual evapotranspiration (ET_{SW1}) using ground-based weather measurements in combination with remote sensing images. As a reference, the validation of SW model to estimate daily actual evapotranspiration (ET_{SW2}) using only climatic data was included. Also, the t-test was used in both cases to check whether the slope (b) was significantly equal to unity at the 95% confidence level.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{n}} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{n} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

$$d = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (|y_i - \hat{y}_i|)}{\sum_{i=1}^n (|y_i| + |\hat{y}_i|^2)} \quad \text{Equation 3} \quad (0 \leq d \leq 1)$$

where, n is the number of observations; y_i is the observed value, and \hat{y}_i is the modeled value.

Results

At 30 min time intervals, the ratio of $(R_n - G)$ to $(H + LE)$ was 0.89, indicating that the orchard energy balance (SEB) was systematically imbalanced by about 11%. Similar results were found by, Williams et al. (2004), Ezzahar et al. (2007), Er-Raki et al. (2010) and Testi et al. (2006). The comparison between observed and estimated values of R_{n_i} , G_i and A_i indicated that the model was able to predict A_i with values of RMSE = 25 W m⁻² and MAE = 21 W m⁻². Also, the t-test indicated that b was significantly different to unity. Values of RMSE and MAE for R_{n_i} ranged between 39 and 32 W m⁻² while those for G_i were 33 and 27 W m⁻², respectively. The t-test showed that R_{n_i} and G_i values were underestimated by about 4 and 8%, respectively. For R_{n_i} , the results are similar to those found in literature for heterogeneous canopies (Teixeira et al, 2009; Carrasco-Benavides et al. 2012; Carrasco-Benavides et al., 2014; Ortega-Farías et al., 2014; Ortega-Farías et al. 2016 and Liu et al. 2007). In the case of G_i the results show a similar performance than those indicated by Shaomin et al. (2007), Carrasco-Benavides et al. (2012), Carrasco-Benavides et al. (2014) and Ortega Farías et al. (2016).

The model validation for ETa estimated through climatic and remote sensing information (ET_{sw1}) indicated RMSE and MAE values of 0.31 and 0.28 mm d⁻¹ respectively. Also, the statistical analysis indicated that the ratio of ET_{sw1} and ETa estimated through Eddy Covariance (ET_{EC}) was significantly equal to the unity. On the other hand, for ETa estimated through climatic information (ET_{sw2}), the results show RMSE and MAE values of 0.46 and 0.44 mm d⁻¹, respectively. The statistical analysis indicated that the ratio of ET_{sw2}/ET_{EC} was significantly different to the unity indicating an error of 10%. Ortega Farías et al., (2006) showed similar results when implementing the SW model in vineyards, where values of RMSE and MAE were 0.42 and 0.36 mm day⁻¹, respectively. Also, Ortega-Farías and Lopez, (2012), indicated that the SW model implemented in an olive orchard (cv. Arbequina), showed a RMSE of 0.52 mm d⁻¹. This information shows that, in this study, errors on the estimation of ETa were within the range of acceptable errors found in literature, and it also highlights the chance of the spatial generation of ETa.

Conclusion

The SW model combined with remote sensing data was applied to estimate values of ETa over a drip-irrigated olive orchard under non-water stress. In relation to this, R_{n_i} and G_i were introduced into the model through A_i . For this, each component was evaluated. For R_{n_i} a RMSE and MAE of 39 W m⁻² and 32 W m⁻² was observed respectively, for G_i RMSE and MAE showed values of 33 W m⁻² and 27 W m⁻². For daily water consumption, the results indicated that ET_{sw1} has RMSE and MAE values of 0.31 and 0.28 mm day⁻¹ respectively. For ET_{sw2} an error of 10% was observed and a RMSE 24% higher than ET_{sw1} . These results indicate that the incorporation of spatially distributed variables such as R_{n_i} and G_i could improve the performance of the model.

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